

THE EFFECT OF A NATURAL-ORIGIN PREPARATION ON THE CONTENT OF REACTIVE OXYGEN SPECIES AND MALONDIALDEHYDE IN COTTON UNDER HEAT STRESS

Nurmatova Munavvar Islomjon qizi¹, Kuldoshova Karomat Mamanazarovna^{1,2}, Akhunov Ali Akhunovich¹, Khashimova Nigora Rustamovna¹

¹A.S. Sadykov Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry. Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences Department, University, Tashkent, 100125, Republic of Uzbekistan

²National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek, Uzbekistan Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovations, Almazor district, 4, University Street, Tashkent, 100174, Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15544241>

Annotation. Our results demonstrate that the protective mechanisms activated by DAG-1 effectively mitigate oxidative stress by reducing the levels of H₂O₂ and MDA. Notably, the application of DAG-1 at a concentration of 10⁻⁷ M has proven to be highly effective in enhancing cotton's tolerance to heat stress and is recommended for field trials aimed at improving cotton resilience under elevated temperature conditions.

Keywords: *G. hirsutum*, *G. barbadense*, cotton, heat stress, DAG-1 compound, reactive oxygen species, malondialdehyde.

Аннотация. Наши результаты показывают, что защитные механизмы, запускаемые ДАГ-1, смягчают окислительный стресс понижая уровень H₂O₂ и МДА. Следует отметить, что применение препарата ДАГ-1 в концентрации 10⁻⁷ М является высокоэффективным для повышения устойчивости хлопчатника к тепловому стрессу и рекомендуется для полевых испытаний для повышения устойчивости хлопчатника к тепловом стрессе.

Ключевые слова: *G. hirsutum*, *G. barbadense*, хлопчатник, тепловой стресс, ДАГ-1 препарат, активных форм кислорода, малонового диальдегида.

Annotatsiya. Bizning tadqiqot natijalarimiz shuni ko'rsatdiki, DAG-1 preparati tomonidan faollashtirilgan himoya mexanizmlari oksidlovchi stressni yumshatadi, bu esa H₂O₂ va MDA miqdorining kamayishi orqali namoyon bo'ladi. Shuni alohida ta'kidlash lozimki, DAG-1 preparatining 10⁻⁷ M konsentratsiyasida qo'llanishi issiqlik stressiga chidamlilikni oshirishda yuqori samaradorlikka ega bo'lib, uni dala sinovlarida qo'llash va paxtaning yuqori haroratga nisbatan chidamliligini oshirish uchun tavsiya etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *G. hirsutum*, *G. barbadense*, g'o'za, issiqlik stressi, DAG-1 preparati, kislorodning faol shakllari, malon dialdegidi.

Introduction

Heat stress, whether short-term or prolonged, induces biochemical alterations in plants, adversely affecting their growth and development, leading to significant yield reductions (1). Elevated temperatures result in excessive production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), causing cellular damage and disruption of cellular organization (2). Mitigating the negative effects of heat stress can be achieved by developing thermotolerant plants through various physiological, biochemical, and genetic approaches.

Currently, international research centers are actively exploring promising and environmentally friendly methods of plant protection using natural compounds that stimulate plant defense mechanisms (3). Compelling evidence has been obtained regarding the impact of natural compounds on enhancing wheat's salinity tolerance (4), maize's cold resistance (5), and tomato's hyperthermia resilience (6).

Among various categories of biostimulants, one successful application in Uzbekistan's cotton cultivation is the DAG-1 preparation. At the Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry named after Academician A.S. Sadykov of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, glycyrrhizic acid (GA) was first isolated from licorice roots, leading to the development of several preparations, including the supramolecular complex with salicylic acid (SA)-DAG-1. This preparation influences cotton's resistance and adaptability to various stresses by stimulating the plant's pro-/antioxidant system.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Plant Material and Heat Stress Treatment

The study utilized cotton plants of *G. hirsutum* (Bukhara-102 variety) and *G. barbadense* (Surkhan-103 variety), obtained through classical breeding methods. Cotton seeds were delinted using concentrated sulfuric acid, followed by thorough rinsing under cold running water for 15 minutes. To assess the impact of DAG-1, delinted seeds were soaked in a 10^{-7} M DAG-1 solution for 12 hours, following the method of Ashim Kumar Das (7). The swollen seeds, wrapped in paper rolls, were germinated for seven days in a moist, dark chamber at 30°C. On the seventh day, half of the seedlings were maintained at 30°C as controls, while the other half were subjected to heat stress by gradually increasing the temperature from 30°C to 45°C at 1°C increments every 10 minutes. Once 45°C was reached, plants were held at this temperature for 6 hours. Post-stress, leaf samples were collected and frozen in liquid nitrogen for subsequent analyses.

2.2. Determination of Hydrogen Peroxide Content

Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) content in cotton leaves was determined using a method based on the detection of molecular iodine formed upon oxidation of potassium iodide (KI) by hydrogen peroxide in an acidic medium (8).

2.3. Determination of Malondialdehyde Content

Malondialdehyde (MDA) levels were analyzed via reaction with 2-thiobarbituric acid (2-TBA), as described by Gur A. *et al.* (9).

3. Results

To evaluate the effect of DAG-1 on ROS and MDA levels in cotton varieties under heat stress, it was found that DAG-1 exhibited a positive and enhanced effect under heat stress in the studied cotton varieties. The influence of DAG-1 on mitigating oxidative stress induced by heat stress was assessed by measuring H₂O₂ content post-treatment with DAG-1 under high-temperature stress and after 24 hours at 30°C. High-temperature stress (45°C) for 6 hours increased H₂O₂ levels in all studied varieties compared to the control temperature (30°C).

Table 1. ROS and MDA content in cotton seedling leaves under prolonged (6 hours) exposure to high temperature (45°C) and after 24 hours at 30°C (nmol/g fresh weight) (n=3; M±m)

Cotton Variety	Control (Untreated)			Treated with the DAG-1	
	Control	Heat Stress 6h (45°C)	After 24h at 30°C	Heat Stress 6h (45°C)	After 24h at 30°C
H₂O₂ Content					

Surkhan-103	117±4	139±5	118±4	111.7±2.8	91.3±3.4
Bukhara-102	159±6	195±7	183±5	109.5±4.6	103.5±4.1
MDA Content					
Surkhan-103	12.5±0.4	14.3±0.5	13.7±0.5	11.3±0.2	9.3±0.2
Bukhara-102	14.8±0.3	17.5±0.4	16.5±0.3	10.4±0.4	9.9±0.1

Pre-treatment with DAG-1 led to a reduction in oxidative stress indicators H₂O₂ and MDA in all studied cotton varieties compared to untreated plants subjected to heat stress. Additionally, a subsequent 24-hour exposure of stressed seedlings to optimal temperature (30°C) further decreased hydrogen peroxide levels in all studied varieties. DAG-1-treated plants showed a reduction in H₂O₂ levels after 24 hours at 30°C post-heat stress: 34% in Surkhan-103 and 47% in Bukhara-102.

In untreated controls, H₂O₂ content correlated with MDA levels, a marker of lipid peroxidation in cells. ROS production resulting from lipid peroxidation can be toxic to membrane lipids, proteins, and DNA. This study noted that heat stress significantly increased lipid peroxidation, potentially due to excessive ROS generation and accumulation. As shown in Table 1, heat stress (45°C) for 6 hours elevated MDA levels in both studied varieties.

Seedlings treated with DAG-1 and subjected to 45°C heat stress exhibited reduced MDA levels compared to untreated plants. Notable reductions were observed in Bukhara-102 (40%) and Surkhan-103 (21%). Similarly, 24 hours post-heat stress cessation, DAG-1-treated plants showed further MDA level reductions: 32% in Surkhan-103 and 40% in Bukhara-102.

4. Discussion

DAG-1 comprises GA and SA, with literature indicating SA as the primary active component. Ashim Kumar and Protik Kumar (7) reported that cotton treated with exogenous SA and subjected to heat stress exhibited a sharp increase in catalase activity, playing a key role in effectively detoxifying H₂O₂ induced by heat stress, thereby ensuring plant survival and resilience under such conditions. The authors noted that SA, a phytohormone known for promoting growth and development, is crucial for enhancing heat stress tolerance in *G. hirsutum* cotton. This improvement is achieved through changes in various biochemical, physiological, and growth parameters.

5. Conclusion

The results indicate that heat stress in two cotton varieties increases ROS and MDA levels. However, treatment with a natural compound led to a reduction in ROS and MDA levels in cotton varieties. Thus, the natural compound contributes to alleviating oxidative stress in cotton.

REFERENCES

1. Hasanuzzaman M., Fujita M. Exogenous Sodium Nitroprusside Alleviates Arsenic-induced Oxidative Stress in Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) Seedlings by Enhancing Antioxidant Defense and Glyoxalase System. *Ecotoxicology*, 2013, 22, 584-596. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10646-013-1050-4>.
2. Khan M.I., Iqbal N., Masood A., Per T.S., Khan N.A. Salicylic acid alleviates adverse effects of heat stress on photosynthesis through changes in proline production and ethylene formation. *Plant Signal Behav.* 2013 Nov;8(11):26374. <https://doi.org/10.4161/psb.26374>.
3. Поликсенова В.Д. Индуцированная устойчивость растений к патогенам и абиотическим стрессовым факторам// Вестник Б.Г.У. 2009. -Т.2. №1.- С.48-60

4. Степанова Е.С. Урожайность видов и сортов озимой пшеницы в зависимости от применения биопрепаратов на засоленных почвах. // Полеводство и луговодство. 2025. №1. -P.16-19 doi:10.24412/0044-3913.
5. Шаркаева Э.Н., Колмыкова Т.С. Влияние природных и синтетических регуляторов роста на растения кукурузы в последствии холодового стресса. //Вестник Мордовского Университета 2011. №4. -P 215-218
6. Sousa B., Rodrigues F., Soares C., Martins M., Azenha M., Lino-Neto T., Santos C., Cunha A., Fidalgo F. Impact of Combined Heat and Salt Stresses on Tomato Plants—Insights into Nutrient Uptake and Redox Homeostasis. *Antioxidants*. 2022; 11(3):478. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antiox11030478>.
7. Das A.K., Ghosh P.K., Nihad S.A., Sultana S, Keya S.S., Rahman M.A., Ghosh T.K., Akter M, Hasan M., Salma U. Salicylic Acid Priming Improves Cotton Seedling Heat Tolerance through Photosynthetic Pigment Preservation, Enhanced Antioxidant Activity, and Osmoprotectant Levels. //Plants. 2024; -Vol.13(12). -P.1639. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants13121639>.
8. Junglee S., Urban L., Sallanon H., Lopez-Lauri, F. (2014) Optimized Assay for Hydrogen Peroxide Determination in Plant Tissue Using Potassium Iodide. *American Journal of Analytical Chemistry*, 5, 730-736. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ajac.2014.511081>.
9. Atilla G., Ufuk D. Diurnal gradual heat stress affects antioxidant enzymes, proline accumulation and some physiological components in cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) // *African Journal of Biotechnology*. 2010.- Vol. 9, №7, pp.1008-1015., Available online at <http://www.academicjournals.org/AJB> <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJB09.1590>